

Synthesis of Disulphonamides*

D. B. INGLE

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad-431 004

and

M. S. SHINGARE

Balbhim College, Beed-431 122

Manuscript received 21 January 1978, revised 22 June 1978, accepted 27 July 1978

A number of disulphonamide derivatives were obtained by a reaction of substituted benzene sulphonyl chloride and substituted benzene sulphonamide or a heterocyclic sulphonamide or vice versa in presence of alkali. They have been confirmed on the basis of their IR spectra. The compounds were tested for the antibacterial activity and found to be inactive.

SOME general ideas about structure activity relationship therapeutically active sulpha drugs are known.

It is reported that shifting the amino group to the meta or ortho position resulted in marked loss of activity¹. Substitution of the amide nitrogen had a variable effect. Methyl and ethyl group did not change the activity while higher alkyl group decreased the activity. Alkylation of the amide nitrogen had no effect on therapeutic efficiency although the compound had lost its water solubility almost completely. However, dimetanilamide had almost the same activity as sulphanilamide. N¹-methyl and N¹-ethyl disulphanilamides have shown promising result on infection caused by the francis stain of influenza in mice². Sulphanilamide derivatives of the general formula $H_2N-C_6H_4-SO_2NH-O_2S-R$ were synthesised where R was alkane³. These compounds showed low chemotherapeutic activity to beta-haemolytic streptococci in mice.

The present paper deals with the synthesis of disulphonamides obtained by the condensation of substituted benzene sulphonylchloride with different benzene sulphonamides or heterocyclic sulphonamides or vice versa in presence of alkali. The main object of the paper was to study the effect of various substituents in the aryl nucleus. An additional interest in preparing these compounds was that some of them contain heterocyclic moiety in one part of the disulphonamides. The heterocyclic nuclei are thiazole, acridine, thiophene, quinoline and coumarin present in one part of some disulphonamides.

The IR spectra of dibenzene disulphonamides gave stretching absorption band in the region 3250-3460 cm^{-1} due to the secondary amine ($-NH-$) and bending absorption band around 1530-1640 cm^{-1}

region. The S=O grouping showed absorption band at 1330-1350 cm^{-1} and 1160-1180 cm^{-1} due to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching respectively.

Experimental

M.P.s. were taken in thiel tube containing liquid paraffin and found to be uncorrected. The spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Perkin-Elmer-137 spectracord.

Synthesis of 4-acetamido-3', 4'-dichlorodibenzene disulphonamides

p-Acetamido benzene sulphonamido (2.149 ; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in water (20 c.c.) containing anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.16 g) and sodium hydroxide (0.3 g) at about 45°. 3,4-Dichlorobenzene sulphonyl chloride (3.0 g ; 0.013 mol) was then added with vigorous agitation over an hour maintaining pH 10 to 11 by the addition of 50% sodium hydroxide solution as required. After stirring for an hour, the reaction mixture was cooled at 10°. The crude product was filtered and dissolved in water whereby the highly soluble salt of 4-acetamido-3', 4'-dichlorodibenzene disulphonamide goes into the solution. The free sodium salt was obtained by the addition of hydrochloric acid or acetic acid. It was crystallised from water. M.P. 155°. Yield 2.10 g (50%).

Similarly all other disulphonamides were prepared. The 2,5-dimethyl-4-thiazole sulphonamide⁴, 5-chloro-7-methoxy-3-sulphonamide acridine⁵, 2-thiophene sulphonyl chloride⁶, 8-quinoline sulphonyl chloride⁷, 3-acetamido-6-sulphonamidocoumarin⁸ were prepared by the known procedure. The melting points, percentage yields and elemental analysis are given in Tables 1 and 2.

*Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists held at Jaipur in December 1977.

INGLE & SHINGARE : SYNTHESIS OF DISULPHONAMIDES

 TABLE-1
 $Ar-SO_2-NH-O_2S-Ar'$

Ar	Ar'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Elemental analysis			
				Found		Calculated	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
4-Acetamidophenyl	3',4'-Dichlorophenyl	155	50	39.90	2.86	39.71	2.83
4-Chlorophenyl	3',4'-Dichlorophenyl	137	40	32.02	2.41	31.87	2.12
4-Chlorophenyl	3'-Nitro-4'-methyl-phenyl	140	35	40.32	3.10	39.94	2.81
4-Chlorophenyl	3'-Chloro-4'-methoxyphenyl	139	35	39.63	2.94	39.39	2.77
4-Bromophenyl	Phenyl	155	40	34.39	3.09	34.09	2.84
4-Bromophenyl	3'-Chloro-4'-methyl-phenyl	127	42	36.37	2.84	36.75	2.59
3-Chloro-6-methyl-phenyl	3'-Chloro-4'-methoxyphenyl	137	42	43.41	3.65	43.07	3.33
3, 4-Dichlorophenyl	3'-Nitro-4'-methyl-phenyl	140	40	36.87	2.57	36.70	2.35
4-Acetamidophenyl	3'-Chloro-6'-methyl-phenyl	135	50	44.95	3.89	44.72	3.72
3-Nitro-4-methyl-phenyl	3'-Chloro-6'-methyl-phenyl	126	35	41.78	3.43	41.53	3.21
4-Methyl-phenyl	4'-Chlorophenyl	210	40	45.37	3.12	45.15	3.47
4-Methyl-phenyl	4'-Bromophenyl	130	40	40.22	3.34	40.00	3.07
4-Methyl-phenyl	2', 5'-Dichlorophenyl	320	40	41.48	3.25	41.05	2.89
3, 4-Dichlorophenyl	2', 5'-Dichlorophenyl	120	35	33.47	1.92	33.10	1.60
3-Carboxy-4-chlorophenyl	4'-Acetamidophenyl	128	40	41.82	3.41	41.62	3.08
3-Nitrophenyl	Phenyl	157	35	42.45	3.24	42.10	2.92
4-Acetamidophenyl	Phenyl	150	45	40.30	4.12	40.45	3.95
3-Chloro-6-methyl-phenyl	3'-Nitro-4'-methyl-phenyl	126	35	41.63	3.40	41.53	3.21
3-Nitro-4-methyl-phenyl	3'-Chloro-4'-methoxyphenyl	240	35	40.18	3.24	39.95	3.09
3-Chloro-4-methoxyphenyl	3'-Chloro-4'-methoxyphenyl	115	40	39.68	3.16	39.43	3.05

TABLE-2

Ar	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Elemental analysis			
				Found		Calculated	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
Phenyl	4-(2',5'-Dimethyl-thiazole)	302	40	39.89	3.74	39.76	3.76
4-Chlorophenyl	4-(2', 5'-Dimethyl-thiazole)	149	35	36.44	3.27	36.00	3.00
4-Bromophenyl	4-(2', 5'-Dimethyl-thiazole)	294	40	32.45	2.82	32.11	2.67
3-Nitrophenyl	4-(2', 5'-Dimethyl-thiazole)	170	35	35.38	3.16	35.01	2.92
Phenyl	3-(5'-Chloro-7'-methoxy acridine)	320	40	52.12	3.36	51.89	3.24
4-Chlorophenyl	2-(Thiophene)	150	40	35.85	2.64	35.55	2.37
4-Bromophenyl	2-(Thiophene)	173	45	31.65	2.38	31.42	2.09
4-Acetamidophenyl	8-(Quinoline)	255	42	53.22	3.96	52.98	3.89
4-Chlorophenyl	8-(Quinoline)	151	40	47.34	2.96	47.05	2.87
4-Chlorophenyl	6-(3'-Acetamidocoumarin)	170	30	44.92	2.98	44.68	2.84
4-Bromophenyl	6-(3'-Acetamidocoumarin)	173	30	41.20	2.72	40.71	2.59

Activity :

Some of the compounds from Tables 1 and 2 were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. typhi* and *V. comma* organism at 200 µg/ml. None of the compounds were found to be effective.

Acknowledgement

Authors thank Dr. M. H. Shah, Assistant Director, Haffkin Institute, Bombay for providing the activity reports. One of the authors (MSS) is grateful to the Marathwada University for the award of research fellowship.

References

1. M. L. CROSSLEY, E. H. NORTHEY and M. E. HULTQUIST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2217.
2. M. L. CROSSLEY, E. H. NORTHEY and M. E. HULTQUIST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2222.
3. M. L. CROSSLEY, E. H. NORTHEY and M. E. HULTQUIST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 1415.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry" 3rd Edition (Longmans, Green & Co., London), 1957, 543.
5. U. P. BASU and S. J. DAS-GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 105.
6. WARBURTON, et al, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4114.
7. MECASLAND, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1946, **11**, 277.
8. Zhur, *Obschel, Khim. J. gen. Chem.*, 1948, **18**, 1449.